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VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

WHEN CEMENT MEETS THE EYE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Ocular injuries from cement dust are rare but can result in significant corneal damage and visual impairment. We present a case of acute exposure to a large amount of cement dust, leading to corneal opacity and reduced visual acuity. Management included immediate irrigation, careful removal of particles and topical medications for pain control and infection prevention. Despite these measures, corneal transplantation may be required if no improvement occurs. This case highlights the serious ocular risks caused by cement dust and shows the importance of rapid assessment, systematic evaluation, and multidisciplinary management. Preventive strategies, especially the use of protective eyewear in occupational settings, are essential to minimize the risk of such injuries and to protect visual function.

KEYWORDS; *Eye trauma, Ocular Emergencies, Foreign body in the eye*

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INTRODUCTION

Foreign body trauma to the eyes is a common reason for emergency room visits. The majority of these patients are male, while the most common foreign bodies are metal objects and dust (1,2). Foreign bodies cause damage in two ways: firstly, these objects can cause penetration leading to related complications, and secondly, they can result in infections and toxicity in the eye. In particular, perforation cases can lead to permanent vision loss depending on the size and type of the object (3). When encountered with these cases in the emergency department, ruling out open globe injuries is crucial. Penetrating injuries should be referred to an ophthalmologist without removal of the foreign body. If the foreign body is superficial, it can be removed by the emergency physician with saline irrigation or with a cotton-tipped applicator under direct visualization using a topical anesthetic (4).

In this case, we present a 15-year-old male patient whose left eye was exposed to cement/hardened sand.

CASE REPORT

A 15-year-old male with a medical history of only attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder presented to the emergency department with exposure to cement/hardened sand to the left eye. The exact mechanism of the injury was uncertain. The patient complained of pain and blurry vision in the left eye. On examination, the left cornea was completely opaque, and there was cement/hardened sand on the upper and lower eyelids. Visual acuity was decreased. Direct and indirect pupillary reflexes were present in both eyes.

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The patient was consulted with ophthalmology with a differential diagnosis of perforation. An examination by the ophthalmologist revealed no perforation but widespread cement particles in the conjunctiva, eyelids, and cornea. Eye irrigation was performed with approximately 1000 cc of saline. A judicial notification was made considering the age and mechanism of the case. The patient was admitted to the eye department for observation and evaluation for surgery. Larger fragments were extracted under a microscope. After an observation period of 4 days with cyclopentolate hydrochloride drops, artificial tear drops, and prednisolone acetate drops, it was not possible to examine and clear the area under the patient's eyelid due to severe pain. Therefore, an operation was planned under general anesthesia, and all eyelids and fornixes were cleared of the particles. The opacity of the cornea had decreased compared to the first visit. However, the patient was referred to another center because of the possible necessity of corneal transplantation.

DISCUSSION

Ocular traumas require a systematic approach to ensure proper diagnosis and management. Following a detailed patient history, visual acuity should be assessed, and both eyes should be examined, including evaluation of pupillary reflexes and extraocular movements. Information regarding contact lens use should be obtained, and any suspicion of orbital fractures should be excluded. Additionally, a prophylactic tetanus shot should be administered if indicated (5). Corneal abrasions caused by foreign bodies are frequently encountered in emergency departments. For superficial

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abrasions, treatment typically focuses on pain control and infection prevention. Topical NSAIDs and artificial tears may be prescribed, while topical antibiotics are commonly prescribed as a precaution (6).

In contrast, chemical injuries can result in extensive damage to the ocular surface epithelium, cornea, and anterior segment, potentially causing permanent visual impairment and necessitating immediate irrigation (7). Cement dust represents a particular occupational hazard, as chronic exposure has been shown to induce corneal dehydration and progressive deterioration of vision in exposed workers (8). In the present case, the patient experienced acute exposure to large quantities of cement dust, leading to significant corneal involvement and reduced visual acuity, highlighting the severity of such injuries.

Penetrating ocular injuries are also common and typically present with hyphema, abnormal pupil or uveal changes, and decreased visual acuity. These injuries may result in long-term complications such as visual loss, traumatic cataract, or secondary infection. Urgent referral to ophthalmology is essential to optimize outcomes and prevent further damage (9).

In our patient, if no improvement is seen with treatment, corneal transplantation is considered as a final therapeutic measure. Corneal blindness remains one of the leading causes of reversible vision loss and can often be successfully treated through keratoplasty. Modern techniques now allow for selective replacement of diseased corneal layers, achieving favorable visual outcomes. Advances in customized component corneal replacement technologies and eye banking methods have further enhanced the success rates of corneal transplantation procedures (10).

This case highlights the rarity of ocular injuries caused by cement dust in the literature, emphasizing the importance of rapid assessment, early intervention, and a multidisciplinary approach. Furthermore, it shows the need for preventive measures, including protective eyewear, particularly in occupational settings where exposure to cement and other hazardous materials may occur.

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